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INVESTIGATION INTO TEACHERS' ASSESSMENT OF LEARNING FOR QUALITY BASIC EDUCATION OUTCOMES IN COVID-19 ERA

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Abstract

The study investigated teachers' assessment of learning for quality basic education outcomes in covid-19 era. Descriptive research design was adopted and population of the study consisted of two hundred and eighty-two (282) teachers in all the public primary schools in Calabar Metropolis in Cross River State. The study population was small and manageable, thus, the census method was adopted in which the entire population was studied. Instrument for data collection was "Enhancing Teachers' Assessment Of Learning Questionnaire" (ETAOL-Q). Developed and validated by the researcher, the instrument had both structured and unstructured sections. The ETAOL-Q instrument was subjected to content and construct validation, with a Cronbach Alpha reliability estimate of 0.82. The researcher visited each school with the help of research assistance and administered the instrument directly to respondents who were required to fill and return same day, while those not seen at the time of first visit, were revisited on schedule. Data collected was analysed using descriptive statistics involving frequency and percentages. Findings confirm gross neglect of affective and psychomotor domains in assessment practice among basic education teachers, and a highlighted long list of challenges as perceived by teachers. Based on the findings, conclusion was drawn and recommendations made among which include urgent workshops, seminars and conferences to be organized for training and retraining program for teachers on innovative instruments for assessment of affective and psychomotor domains.

Introduction

Education at all era has been known to constitute the bedrock of the development of all countries of the world. However, the type of education which facilitates national development must necessarily be qualitative especially at the basic level. This implies that quality basic education is a precursor to sustainable national development particularly in the education sector. Teachers at the basic education level play critical roles towards ensuring the delivery of qualitative education for national development.

Quality for primary or basic education has been aptly described as the extent to which the process of education maximises desirable outcomes in terms of cognitive, affective and psychomotor behaviour of the learners (Nenty, Adedoyin,

Odili & Major, 2007). Teachers are the fulcrum around which the achievement of the desirable (quality) educational outcome revolves. Therefore, these teachers especially at the basic educational level must possess the requisite skills and personality not only to deliver instructional services but to adopt international best practices for the assessment of their students. In spite of the introduction and implementation of a new and robust 9-year basic education policy in Nigeria, teachers at this level of education are perceived to lack the capacities to adequately and objectively assess the learners. The perceived incompetence in assessment practices among teachers at the basic education level have been supported by research findings of scholars like; Nenty (2008); Nenty and Fetogang (2014);

Ugodulunwa and Imo (2015), Idika and Ovat (2017); Asim (2018); Ikwuanusi and Ukah (2018), to mention a few. One of such incompetences is the perceived neglect of the affective and psychomotor domains. Even within the cognitive domain which has received more emphasis of basic teachers, much effort has concentrated on the memory, comprehension and application levels of cognition, while the higher order levels of synthesis, evaluation and creativity that provide the needed 21st century qualitative skills are observably neglected (Nenty, 2007; Emeka & Obialo, 2010). Nenty & Fetogang (2015) also saw this as a serious challenge while insisting that embedding the educational requirements to the needs of the society requires that these skills which are relevant to a developing nation with specific goals and visions be emphasized in the teaching, learning and assessment process of education.

The 9-3-4 system of education in Nigeria stresses the objective assessment of the educational outcomes based on the three domains of learning; cognitive, psychomotor and affective domains. This implies that teachers at the basic education level must address instructional content and adequate assessment of the three domains. For instance, if learners must contribute maximally to national development, they must possess high order thinking and creative skills which must be assessed through high level cognitive questions. This perceived neglect of the affective and psychomotor domains in the assessment practices by basic education teachers' inability to reflect at higher levels within the cognitive domain being focused at, may pose palpable and grave challenges to the desired achievement of quality basic education for national development.

It is quite apparent that the non-coverage of domains of learning in teachers' assessment was a challenge that existed till the emergence of the Covid-19, which itself is a stress on the assessment process in the education system. That being the case, the researcher suggest that something needs to

be done instantly considering that all these perceived challenges in adjusting to the "new normal" by teachers in their assessment procedures or methods could add up to the existing challenges to further bring about a decline in quality of basic education. It is against this back drop that this study seeks to explore ways of enhancing teachers' assessment of learning for quality basic education outcomes in covid-19 era

Theoretical Framework

This study finds its backing on Instructional theory by Robert Gagne which was propounded in 1962. The instructional theory seeks to describe the conditions under which one can intentionally arrange for the learning of specific performance outcomes. Gagne believes it was important for teachers and instructional designers to think carefully about the nature of the skill or-task they wanted to teach in order to be sure the learner had the necessary prerequisites to acquire that skill. Gagne (1962) also emphasized that practice and assessment should match the target skill.

This theory has three major elements. First; it is based on taxonomy of learning outcomes. Second, it proposes particular internal and external conditions necessary for achieving these learning outcomes. And third, it offers nine events of instruction, which serve as a template for developing and delivering each unit of instruction. The relevance of this theory to this study is that the principle of the theory relates to ensuring the delivery of qualitative education at all levels of education, particularly at basic education. This theory brings to bare how the teacher should plan and organize their lesson in order to bring about better understanding in the learner and simultaneously establish the basis of evaluation and or assessment of learning in the different domains of learning outcome. For example, the three events or conditions of instruction, if satisfactorily executed, should give the teacher the impetus for

utilization of quality or appropriate assessment strategies.

Literature review

A good number of authors are in agreement that quality in the outcome of education can be achieved when items that reflect the various levels in the learning domains are comprehensively mirrored in the assessment procedures particularly at the basic level (Nwana, 2007; Ogomaka, 2009; Ojerinde, 2011; Offor, 2014). Nenty, Adedoyin, Odili and Major (2007) carried out a survey to determine the extent to which primary school teachers in Botswana and Nigeria perceived the six levels of Bloom's cognitive behaviour as being different in the extent to which they enhance quality in primary education and the level to which their current classroom assessment practices involve items that measure each of these levels of cognitive behaviour. The study made use of survey data from 191 primary school teachers from Garborne district in Botswana and 300 similar teachers from Delta state in Nigeria, and these were analysed using repeated ANOVA to test related hypotheses. The results showed that primary school teachers in Botswana and Nigeria through their classroom assessment practices did not contribute significantly to the quality of basic education. In other words, the results had not shown that the teachers' assessment practices provided much for the growth among their pupils, of cognitive skills with which they can find solution to real life problems, for creativity and for critical thinking and judgement. It is important to note that the most important aspects of the changes which are desired in our basic learners through the procedure of assessment are tied strongly to the amount, type and level of the cognitive, affective and psychomotor skills that are developed among these learners. Learners that have critical thinking, problem-solving, creative and higher order thinking skills well cultivated in them are already on their way to meeting the necessary demands for proper adaptation and adequate contribution

to the rapidly changing information and labour force economy of the world. Several other studies on assessment exist which are strong expressions of the authors over the attitude of classroom teachers towards the use of effective assessment practices in our school system to effect the quality of education. They have all lent their voices in the recommendation for assessment practice that would be comprehensive and authentic enough to include the three domains of learning (Joshua, 2005; Nenty et al 2007; Kasilingam et al, 2014; Ugodulunwa and Imo, 2015; Idika and Ovat, 2017; Ikwuanusi and Ukah, 2018; Nwokocha and Adamu, 2018). The poor state of the assessment practices as lamented by those authors seem not to have received improvement over the past years and now, COVID-19 pandemic with occasioned lock down arrived which has presented additional burden on the relevant authorities to position schools particularly at the basic level in order to meet with new demands of the 'new normal'. In their assessment of learning domains to improve students' learning in higher education in Malaysia, Kasilingam, Ramalingam and Chinnavan (2014), even though their scope or attention was on higher education and the engineering part of it, the study's aim to improve the identified existing vague assessment methods that failed to show concrete continual quality improvement in education, was something to reckon with. The result of the study showed the development of their proposed online interfacing with face-to-face assessment method which is more holistic to assess the cognitive, affective and psychomotor behaviours of individual learners. However, the question this paper seems to be bothered with is: Do basic teachers really have the capacity to utilize the innovative assessment methods which are mostly online environments supportive as demanded in the face of the COVID-19 pandemic in all 3 domains to effectively achieve a high level of improvement in the quality of education at this fundamental level? In other-words, can the teachers

while observing all the protocols of COVID-19 be able to assess basic children using assessment tools considered to be encompassing and innovative (mostly online) in the cognitive domain to improve knowledge acquisition, and in the affective and psychomotor domains to improve character and skill development? To what extent can basic teachers, male and female, in the face of COVID-19 engage assessment tools in all levels of domains in a way as to contribute effectively to the enhancement of quality of basic education and education in general? Going through the existing literature on this subject matter, the answer to the questions above can hardly be in the affirmative. This further corroborates the observation that most schools in Nigeria have not met the minimum safety standard that would apply to ensure proper academic activities (Federal Ministry of Education, 2006). In the same vein, it is a widely held view in literature that the nature of females is perceived to be an issue in what they can handle at a given time as far as schools' tasks are concerned.

However, — following the development of a holistic assessment method that can take care of the cognitive, affective & psychomotor domains though at a higher education level by Kasiligam et al (2014), and a few number of studies whose findings have endorsed the recommendation of use of effective and authentic measures to achieve assessment of students' learning, there appear to be hope in the assessment procedure as a means of enhancing the quality of education in Nigeria. But the challenge remains that these studies were neither focused on the basic level of education nor in the time of crisis such as COVID-19.

Purpose of the study

Generally, the study focused on enhancing teachers' assessment of learning for quality basic education outcomes in covid-19 era. Specifically, the study sought to;

- i. confirm from teachers the learning domain they prefer to assess
- ii. determine the perceived challenges of assessment in the domains being neglected
- iii. recommend measures that can enhance teachers assessment of the neglected domains

Research questions

The following research questions guided the study;

- i. What are the learning domains teachers prefer to assess?
- ii. What are the perceived challenges of assessment in the domains being neglected?

Methodology

Descriptive research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study consists of two hundred and eighty-two (282) teachers in all the public primary schools in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State. The study population was small and manageable, thus, the census method was adopted in which the entire population was studied. Instrument for data collection was "Enhancing Teachers' Assessment of Learning Questionnaire" (ETAOL-Q) which was developed and validated by the researchers. The instrument was both structured and unstructured and consisted of three parts: part 1 contained items on respondents' demographic data, while part 2 contained items measuring the various sub-variables of the study. Respondents were required to rate their opinion on a four-point scale. The instrument was subjected to content and construct validation, with reliability check after trial on a sample of 50 primary school teachers in neighbouring Akpabuyo Local Government Area of Cross River State. Data obtained from the trial test was subjected to reliability estimate using Cronbach Alpha reliability formula which yielded reliability estimate of 0.82. On the strength of the high reliability index, the instrument was considered suitable to be

used for the study. The researcher visited each school and with the help of research assistants administered copies of the instrument directly to respondents who were required to fill and return them on the same day, while those not seen at the time of first visit, were revisited on schedule. For ease of data preparation, a coding schedule was prepared by developing a key for each of the items of the instruments in a tabular form, from where data was extracted for analysis.

Data collected was analysed using descriptive statistics involving frequency and percentages.

Results and discussion

Results of the study were presented according to the research questions of the study;

Table 1
Demographic data of respondents

S/N	Variable	Category	N	Percent (%)
1	Gender	Male	114	40.42
		Female	168	59.58
		Total	282	100.00
2	Age	18 – 35	38	13.47
		36 – 45	82	29.07
		46 – 55	75	26.59
		56 and above	87	30.85
		Total	282	100.00
3	Marital status	Single	68	24.11
		Married	161	57.09
		Divorced	16	5.67
		Separated	17	6.02
		Widow	14	4.96
		Widower	6	2.12
4	Educational qualification	Total	282	100.00
		NCE	176	62.41
		B.SC/BA/HND	97	34.39
		PGD/M.Sc./Ph.D	9	3.19
		Total	282	100.00

Research question one:

What are the learning domains teachers prefer to assess most?

Descriptive statistics involving frequencies and percentages were used to analyse data to answer the research question. The result is presented in table 2.

Table 2
Teachers' preference of assessment of learning domains

S/N	Learning domains	N	F (%)	Remarks
1	Affective	282	3 (1.06)	N/P
2	Cognitive	282	277 (98.22)	M/P
3	Psychomotor	282	2 (0.71)	N/P

Key: N/P = Not preferred, M/P = Most preferred

From the results as presented in table 2, findings reveal that teachers at basic education level prefer to conduct assessment in the cognitive domain more than the affective and psychomotor domains. This is evident in the number of teachers who indicated preference for cognitive = 277 representing 98.22% of total respondents, affective = 3 (1.06), and psychomotor 2 (0.71). The implication here, is that teachers at the basic education level grossly neglect assessment in the psychomotor and affective domains of learning.

Research question two:

What are the perceived challenges of assessment in the domains (affective and psychomotor) being neglected?

Descriptive statistics involving frequencies and percentages were used to analyse data and to answer the research question. All the challenges as listed by teachers were clustered into 20 basic challenges. An item was considered a challenge if listed by at least 50% of the respondents. The challenges were also categorised into moderate challenge (MC), serious challenge (SC) and very serious challenge (VSC) based on the number and percentage of respondents who listed them and, the result is presented in table 3.

Table 3
Challenges of assessment in the domains being neglected (affective and psychomotor) as perceived by teachers

S/N	Perceived challenges	N	F (%)	Remarks
1	Do not know instruments to use for assessment in the affective and psychomotor domains	282	264 (93.61)	VSC
2	Difficulty in constructing instruments for affective and psychomotor domains assessment	282	271 (96.09)	VSC
3	How to score pupils in the affective and psychomotor domains	282	268 (95.03)	VSC
4	Do not know exactly what to assess in the affective and psychomotor domains	282	266 (94.32)	VSC
5	Where to include affective and psychomotor domains in specific objective in lesson notes	282	278 (98.58)	VSC
6	Difficult to get appropriate action verb for the expression of affective and psychomotor domains	282	255 (90.42)	VSC
7	It is not easy to achieve affective and psychomotor domains objectives within a lesson period of forty minutes	282	261 (92.55)	VSC
8	High pupils/teacher ratio	282	223 (79.07)	SC
9	Non utilization of the results of affective and psychomotor domains assessment in decision-making such as promotion and certification	282	275 (97.51)	VSC
10	Lack of enthusiasm on the part of the teachers about assessing pupils for affective and psychomotor domains purposes	282	164 (58.15)	MC
11	Subjectivity in the ratings of affective and psychomotor domains behavioural traits	282	197 (69.85)	SC
12	Influence of social factors that could make a child manifest several behaviours at a time	282	172 (60.99)	SC
13	Tendency for teachers to input motives to the actions of students or bring in personal feelings into the recording of his observation of students behaviorin	282	152 (53.90)	MC

	affective and psychomotor domains			
14	Difficulty in getting true or reliable results from assessment as pupils could fake their attitudes	282	267 (94.68)	VSC
15	Values, attitudes, sentiments, prejudices, emotions and many other affective traits change very rapidly, so what a teacher discovers from his assessment in the affective and psychomotor domains area today may become useless, untrue or misleading the following day	282	244 (86.52)	VSC
16	It is not used for purpose of decision-making, job placement, promotion, certification or admission into institutions of learning	282	281 (99.64)	VSC
17	Effective assessment on affective and psychomotor domains depends on the amount of observation which the teacher can carry out on the students concerned	282	240 (85.10)	VSC
18	No teacher training programme on assessment in affective and psychomotor domains	282	282 (100.00)	VSC
19	Lack of time required for direct observation of procedural skills in psychomotor	282	278 (98.58)	VSC
20	No motivation from government	282	277 (98.22)	VSC

Key: MC = Moderate challenge (50-60%), SC = Serious challenge (61-80%), VSC = Very serious challenge (81-100%)

Results as presented in table 3 revealed a myriad of challenges perceived by teachers to be responsible for the neglect of assessment in the affective and psychomotor domains. All the challenges as listed by teachers were clustered into 20 basic challenges and responses; selection being based on challenges listed by at least 50% of the respondents as follows; out of 282 respondents 264 representing 93.61% indicated that they do not know instruments to use for assessment in the affective and psychomotor domains. This was considered a very serious challenge (VSC). 271 (96.09) respondents listed difficulty in constructing instruments for affective and psychomotor domains assessment (VSC); 268 (95.03) mentioned that their challenge is how to score pupils in the affective and psychomotor domains (VSC); 266 (94.32) respondents do not know exactly what to assess in the affective and psychomotor domains (VSC); 278 (98.58) respondents did not know where to include affective and psychomotor domains in specific objective in lesson notes (VSC); 255 (90.42) mentioned that it is difficult to get

appropriate action verb for the expression of affective and psychomotor domains (VSC), it is not easy to achieve affective and psychomotor domains objectives within a lesson period of forty minutes = 261 (92.55) (VSC), high pupils/teacher ratio = 223 (79.07), this was considered a serious challenge (SC), non-utilization of the results of affective and psychomotor domains assessment in decision-making such as promotion and certification = 275 (97.51), lack of enthusiasm on the part of the teachers about assessing pupils for affective and psychomotor domains purposes = 164 (58.15) this was considered a moderate challenge (MC), subjectivity in the ratings of affective and psychomotor domains behavioural traits = 197 (69.85) (SC), influence of social factors that could make a child manifest several behaviours at a time = 172 (60.99) (SC), tendency for teachers to input motives to the actions of students or bring in personal feelings into the recording of his observation of students behavior in affective and psychomotor domains = 152 (53.90) (MC), difficulty in getting true or reliable results from assessment as pupils

could fake their attitudes = 267 (94.68) (VSC). Similarly, 244 (86.52) respondents mentioned that values, attitudes, sentiments, prejudices, emotions and many other affective traits changes very rapidly, so what a teacher discovers from his assessment in the affective and psychomotor domains area today may become useless, untrue or misleading the following day (VSC), it is not used for purpose of decision-making, job placement, promotion, certification or admission into institutions of learning =281 (99.64) (VSC), effective assessment on affective and psychomotor domains depends on the amount of observation which the teacher can carry out on the students concerned = 240 (85.10) (VSC), no teachers training programme on assessment in affective and psychomotor domains = 282 (100.00) (VSC), lack of time required for direct observation of procedural skills in psychomotor =278 (98.58) (VSC) and no motivation from government = 277 (98.22) (VSC).

Discussion

The results of this study confirm that teachers at basic education level prefer to conduct assessment in the cognitive domain more than the affective and psychomotor domains. The implications are that teachers at the basic education level grossly neglect assessment in the psychomotor and affective domains of learning, leading to poor evaluation of learning outcomes at that level of education as pupils who may not be good in cognition as in affective and psychomotor traits are bound to suffer deprivations. Scholars in the assessment field are in agreement that quality in the outcome of education can be achieved when assessment comprehensively reflects the various learning domains in the assessment procedures. Results of the study support the findings of Nenty, Adedoyin, Odili and Major (2007) which showed that primary school teachers in Botswana and Nigeria through their classroom assessment practices did not contribute significantly to the quality of basic education, owing to poor

and lopsided assessment practices. It is even more worrisome that the findings of this present study corroborates with strong evidence, that of a study conducted in 2007, a clear indication that the problem still persists.

Furthermore, the study attempted to explore possible challenges to this trend of neglecting assessment in affective and psychomotor domains. The results as presented in table 3, revealed a list of 20 challenges mentioned by the respondents (teachers). The challenges listed were selected and clustered into 20 basic challenges; selection being based on challenges listed by at least 50% of the respondents; and the challenges were also categorised into moderate challenge (MC), serious challenge (SC) and very serious challenge (VSC) based on the number and percentage of respondents who listed them thus; MC = Moderate challenge (50-60%), SC = Serious challenge (61-80%), VSC = Very serious challenge (81-100%).

Findings revealed that teachers' challenges in this regard range from not knowing instruments to use for assessment in the affective and psychomotor domains, lack of training on how to conduct assessment in affective and psychomotor domains, high pupil/teacher ratio to absence of motivation, to mention a few. Findings of this study also support earlier position of some scholars in this field of learning (Joshua, 2005; Nenty et al, 2007; Ogomaka, 2009; Ojerinde, 2011, Kasilingam et al, 2014; Offor, 2014; Ugodulunwa & Imo, 2015; Idika and Ovat, 2017; Iwuanusi and Ukah, 2018; Asim, 2018;) who all lamented the poor and incompetent practice in assessment going on among teachers.

The result is not surprising at all. A situation where a teacher handles a class of between 40- 50 pupils in the primary school and between 25-30 lesson periods in a week, it may be very challenging for him to evaluate all the pupils in various aspects of affective and psychomotor behaviour, and maintain the record consistently.

Conclusion

The present study aimed at investigating teachers' assessment of learning for quality basic education outcomes in covid-19 era in view of the wide speculations bordering on incomprehensive assessment among teachers, in order to make policy recommendation for solutions to the menace. Study findings confirmed gross neglect of affective and psychomotor domains in assessment practice among basic education teachers, and that the trend had continued for many years, as present results corroborate previous findings; a situation capable of depriving pupils gifted in the affective and psychomotor traits, and slowing down opportunities to identify young geniuses for national development.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Urgent workshops, seminars and conferences should be organized for training and retraining program for teachers on instruments for assessment of affective and psychomotor domains.
2. Teachers should be motivated to carryout consistent observation and recording of pupils' affective and psychomotor behaviours.
3. The results of assessment of affective and psychomotor domains should be utilized for many purposes in the Nigerian society such as decision-making, job placement, promotion, certification or admission into institutions of learning.

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